

Registration of Manh-Tan Le for Participation in BMF CP 101 on children engagement with nature and pro-environmental behaviors.

Manh-Tan Le

Lecturer, Faculty of Marine Economics – Logistics, Ba Ria-Vung Tau University (BVU), Vietnam

Email: tanlm@bvu.edu.vn/ manhtant08@gmail.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-9781-8977>

By registering to participate in the project titled “BMF CP101: The influence of engaging children with nature interactions to pro-environmental behaviors under different conditions” through the mindsponge.info portal, I affirm that I have fully understood, agreed with, and committed to adhering to the philosophy, principles, and ethical standards that the research community upholds [1].

In this research, I will assume the role of co-author, responsible for the Materials and Methods section based on publicly available data. At the same time, I also commit to providing further support if any professional requirements arise from the team leader (Mr. Vu) to contribute to the team.

I sincerely thank mindsponge.info for building a platform where young researchers like me have the opportunity to connect with people who share the same passion for science.

I affirm that the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) [2] will be applied scientifically and ethically in the development of the conceptual framework, the conduct of experimental analysis, and the interpretation of results. In the spirit of openness and transparency, our research manuscript will publicly share data, code, analytical procedures, and preliminary results, in order to maintain integrity and ethical standards in science.

References

[1] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH (2025). Developing Bayesian probabilistic reasoning capacity in HSS disciplines: Qualitative evaluation on bayesvl and BMF analytics for ECRs.

<https://dipot.ulb.ac.be/dspace/bitstream/2013/397326/3/wp25008.pdf>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP (2022) *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter.

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Manh-Tan Le